

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles.

Part III.

BY

PRAFULLA CHANDRA RÂY, BIRES CHANDRA GUHA

AND

KSHITISH CHANDRA BOSE-RÂY.

The remarkable complex compounds derived from platonic chloride and ethyl sulphide, which have been described in a foregoing communication (this *Journal*, 1925, 2, 178), have now been subjected to treatment with ammonia and organic bases. The results obtained have thrown considerable light on their constitutions (*loc. cit.*). The products formed are well-known compounds of the Werner type. The evidence is, therefore, directly corroborative of the Werner constitution of the compounds studied, as already suggested.

In the present paper the action of ammonia and pyridine on some of the isomeric varieties of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and on $\text{PtCl}_3, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_4, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ has been studied.

Action of Ammonia and Pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

By the action of ammonia $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ is converted into $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{NH}_3$; $2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ is thus replaced by 4NH_3 . This may be most conveniently represented on the Werner model as follows:—

Cl non-ionisable

Cl ionisable

Almost all the modifications of $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ gave a

the constitution $[(Et_2S)_2.PtCl_3].[(Et_2S)_2.PtCl_3]$. Further confirmation is now brought forward by studying the action of ammonia. From the resulting products a compound of the composition $PtCl_2, 4NH_3$ has been isolated, which has been evidently derived from the first component of the molecular compound depicted above. The product of the action of ammonia on the other component has not been isolated. The other proposed formula for this compound, *viz.*, $[Pt(Et_2S)_4]PtCl_2$ (*cf.* Tschugaeff, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 420) might be expected to give a compound of the empirical composition $Pt(NH_3)_2Cl_3$, but no such compound has been so far isolated.

Action of Ammonia and Pyridine on $PtCl_4, 2Et_2S$.

Ammonia is found to give the compound $PtCl_4, 4NH_3$ and pyridine the compound $PtCl_4, 2Py$, which readily lend themselves to interpretation on the Werner basis, thus :

Compounds (III) and (IV) are well-known and can have no other constitutions than those suggested above. It is of interest to note here that these compounds, which had been obtained by previous workers direct from platinous chloride, etc., have now been obtained in quite a different way.

The replacement of Et_2S by ammonia and organic bases seems to occur step by step in at least some of the reactions of the above type (*cf.* Klason, *Ber.*, 1875, 28, 1496; *J. pr. Chem.* [2] 67, 33, 39; *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1359 etc.). Some intermediate compounds of this variety will be described in a future communication.

The compounds PtCl , Et_2S and $\text{PtCl}_5(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are of uncertain constitution and are also under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, m. p. 96°.

The compound was dissolved in a very small quantity of alcohol and an excess of alcoholic ammonia was added. The odour of ethyl sulphide was distinctly perceptible and in the course of some ten minutes the solution became colourless and white crystals began to separate out. After half-an-hour the first crop was filtered off, which being impure, was rejected. The filtrate on standing for three or four hours more deposited a second crop of colourless crystals, which were well washed with alcohol, dried between the folds of a filter-paper and kept for some time in a desiccator. (Found: Pt=58·68; Cl=20·87; N=15·28. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4(\text{NH}_3)$ requires Pt=58·63; Cl=21·13; N=16·67 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, m.p. 104°.

The compound was dissolved in a moderately large volume of alcohol and alcoholic ammonia was added. On standing for 6-7 hours long colourless needles crystallised out. These were washed with alcohol and dried in a desiccator. (Found: Pt=58·52; Cl=21·36; N=15·61 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, m. p. 108°.

The compound was dissolved in benzene and dry ammonia gas passed into it so as to remove the ethyl sulphide from the sphere of reaction as soon as it was formed. The turbid solution was filtered and the filtrate spontaneously evaporated in a desiccator. The yellowish-white product was washed first with alcohol, then with

benzene (in both of which it is sparingly soluble) until the product was white and again finally it was washed with alcohol and then dried for 3 hours in a desiccator. (Found : Pt=59.79 Cl=21.55 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, m. p. 110°.

Gaseous ammonia was passed through an alcoholic solution of the compound when gradually colourless crystals came down which were filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. (Found : Cl=22.37 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, m. p. 77°.

The compound was digested with a small quantity of pyridine on a water-bath for about half-an-hour until the whole thing went into solution. The solution on standing deposited small needles and on again warming the solution and standing a considerable quantity of yellow crystals came down. These were filtered, washed with a little pyridine and then with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The compound shrinks at 260° and chars between 270° and 280°. It was crystallised from chloroform. It is practically insoluble in alcohol. (Found : Pt=46.37, 46.16; Cl=17.39; N=7.18. $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt=46.24; Cl=16.66 and N=6.57 per cent.). The above platinum compound was also directly treated with pyridine in the cold. The compound dissolved and gradually a yellowish crystalline deposit was thrown down. After washing with a little pyridine and then with alcohol several times the substance melted at 175—76°. The mother-liquor, on being allowed to evaporate to dryness spontaneously, deposited fine white hexagonal plates which unlike the yellow compound were extremely soluble in water. (Found : Cl=11.58; N=9.32. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{Py}$ requires Cl=12.1; N=9.6 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia on PtCl₃, 2Et₂S.—The substance was suspended in a very small quantity of water into which ammonia gas was passed. The compound slowly dissolved, giving finally a colourless solution. The solution was concentrated in a desiccator when colourless crystals separated out. These were filtered off, washed rapidly with very little water and dried for 4 hours in a desiccator. The filtrate on complete evaporation in a desiccator deposited another substance which, however, was brownish coloured and could not be sufficiently purified for analysis. (Found: Pt=58.68; Cl=21.31; N=17.09. PtCl₂, 4NH₃ requires Pt=58.53; Cl=21.13 and N=16.67 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia on PtCl₄, 2Et₂S.—The resulting compound was isolated in this case after several trials. Dry ammonia gas was passed for some 15 minutes into a benzene solution of the substance. The precipitate formed was filtered and washed with benzene and dried in a desiccator. (Found: Pt=48.13; Cl=34.44; N=16.68. PtCl₄, 4NH₃ requires Pt=48.4; Cl=34.9; N=17.2 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on PtCl₄, 2Et₂S.—The compound was treated with a little pyridine and as it went into solution, yellow crystals began to separate out. After standing for 1-2 hours they were filtered, washed well with pyridine, alcohol, acetone and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found: Pt=39.92; Cl=28.06; N=6.15. PtCl₄, 2C₅H₅N requires Pt=39.6; Cl=28.5 and N=5.6 per cent.).